

DEVELOPING THE CREATIVITY OF FUTURE MUSIC EDUCATION TEACHERS IN AN INNOVATIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the scientific and theoretical basis for developing creative thinking, independent thinking, and creativity in future music teachers based on innovative pedagogical technologies, digital tools, and interactive methods.

Keywords: Creativity, innovative learning environment, pedagogical technologies, creativity, methodological approach, digital tools.

INTRODUCTION

One of the current principles of higher education is the coordination of the activities of higher educational institutions in the preparation of future specialists and mentors as highly qualified, creative specialists, and the application of pedagogical innovations to the educational process based on a creative approach to the creation and reform of an innovative educational environment.

Innovative activity implies a creative approach by a future specialist to master existing forms and means of improving his profession.

An innovative educational environment is an educational environment organized on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies, digital tools and interactive methods, which is aimed at developing the skills of future teachers to think independently, solve problems and adopt a creative approach.

The future teacher, as a subject and organizer of an innovative educational environment, participates in the creation, application and popularization of innovation. He must be able to analyze the content and essence of changes in knowledge and traditions in the subject.

Creativity is a characteristic of an individual's readiness to generate new ideas and expresses the meaning of creative ability, which is part of talent as an independent factor. A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, emotions, and certain types of activity.

Music education is not only the process of teaching theoretical knowledge and technical skills, but also an important means of developing a person's inner world, aesthetic views, and creative potential. In this regard, creativity is considered a fundamental concept.

Creativity in music education is not just an aesthetic aspect, but a central element of methodological, psychological, and pedagogical approaches. A creative teacher inspires music lessons, inspires students, and helps to reveal their inner potential. Therefore, the development of creativity is an important strategic task in the training of future music teachers.

In the modern education system, the teacher is required not only to impart knowledge, but also to develop the student's independent thinking, innovative approach to the problem, and creative potential. Especially in music education, creativity is one of the main competencies.

Therefore, the formation of creativity of future music teachers is one of the most important stages in their professional training.

In the context of the pedagogical process aimed at forming the creativity of future music teachers, pedagogical skills are of great importance, which include the formation of qualities such as musical pedagogical creativity, the ability to solve educational situations and problems, and an understanding of pedagogical technology and creativity in innovative education.

In the modern education system, the teacher is required not only to impart knowledge, but also to develop the student's independent thinking, innovative approach to the problem, and creative potential. Especially in music education, creativity is one of the main competencies. Therefore, the formation of creativity of future music teachers is one of the most important stages in their professional training.

In the context of the pedagogical process aimed at forming the creativity of a future music teacher, pedagogical skills are of great importance, which include the formation of such qualities as musical pedagogical creativity, the ability to solve educational situations and problems, and an understanding of pedagogical technology and creativity in innovative education. Today, one of the main tasks set before a modern educational institution is the search, creation and implementation of educational innovations aimed at meeting the public-state order and the needs of participants in the educational process.

In conclusion, we note that the considered innovative approaches and relevant educational technologies help to solve the following urgent tasks of modern higher education: effective assimilation of knowledge; formation of practical research skills that allow making professional decisions; transition from the accumulation of knowledge to the creation of mechanisms for the formation of independent search and research skills; formation of value orientations of the student's personality; increasing cognitive activity; development of creative abilities; creation of didactic and psychological conditions that contribute to the successful social adaptation of students.

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